

Perception of Tertiary Institution Students in Lagos State on the use of Podcast Media as a Learning Tool

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17259785>

Abstract

This study investigated the perception of tertiary institution students in Lagos state on the use of podcast media as a learning tool. The technology acceptance model was the theoretical framework used to support this study. The study adopted a survey design. Data were collected from three tertiary institutions in Lagos state; namely: University of Lagos, Yaba Tech and FCE, technical Akoka, Lagos, respectively with a sample size of one thousand one hundred and twenty-nine (1129). A validated questionnaire was used to gather responses using the convenience sampling method. The data were analysed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) where descriptive statistics, frequencies and percentages, were used to present data and explore the relationships between variables. Findings from the study revealed that podcast media is widely known and perceived positively by tertiary institutions' students in Lagos state. In addition, podcast media influences social interaction of students as they interact with one another sharing thoughts and opinions on several topics. The study concluded that the podcast media is a potential learning tool but remains underutilised due to awareness and curricular integration challenges. The study, therefore, recommended integrating podcasts in education, promoting and fostering creativity through course-specific podcasts and digital content labs.

Keywords: Podcast, Learning tool, Knowledge, Perception, Behaviour, Habits

Introduction

The emergence of the digital era has introduced a revolutionary medium that is altering our methods of information consumption, storytelling and interaction with varied material. A powerful and easily accessible medium, podcasting is upending conventional broadcasting and elevating voices from all over the globe. Ifedayo (2023) is of the opinion that in the age of digitisation and the democratisation of content production, podcasts have emerged as a transformational medium with worldwide consequences. Podcasting, as a potent and accessible medium, has established its position in the media landscape, contesting conventional broadcasting and elevating voices from diverse global perspectives (Pelegrín, 2023). Podcasting fundamentally serves as a medium that surpasses geographical limitations. It transcends the boundaries of certain countries or areas; it is a worldwide phenomenon. The emergence of podcasting is not only a reflection of the developed world's digital progress; it is a worldwide symphony of voices, each with its own rhythm and message (Bonini, 2022).

Podcasting has clearly acquired worldwide appeal and is increasingly being integrated into school, serving as a vital learning tool, particularly for young people. The importance of integrating podcasting in education arises from its capacity to facilitate distance learning, encourage self-directed learning, provide an innovative method for supporting educational endeavours, enhance collaborative learning and online education, and accommodate various learning styles, thereby addressing the needs of learners encountering educational challenges (Hassan 2024). Additionally, the platform makes it easier for educators to engage with students and gives them the tools they need to properly instruct them. Notwithstanding these advantages, enquiries persist over the extent to which students have effectively used the many benefits that podcast media provides, particularly as a medium for learning and socialisation. This might provide a considerable obstacle for podcasters seeking to use this platform for educational and societal advancement.

Lagos State, being Nigeria's economic and educational centre, accommodates various higher institutions with varied student demographics. Despite the increased prevalence of smartphone and internet utilisation among students in the state, it remains ambiguous if these digital resources are being used for educational objectives, such as podcast learning. Anecdotal research indicates that many students mostly use digital media for social and entertainment objectives, whereas their recognition and understanding of podcasts as academic resources may be constrained or insufficiently developed.

Currently, there is an absence of empirical evidence about students' understanding of podcast media, their views of its educational significance and the variables affecting its use as a learning instrument in Lagos State. In the absence of such data, educational institutions and policymakers may overlook possibilities to successfully incorporate podcasts into learning processes, particularly in blended or distant learning environments. This study, therefore, seeks to investigate the knowledge and perception of students in tertiary institutions in Lagos State regarding the use of podcast media as a learning tool.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the perception of tertiary institution students in Lagos state on the use of podcast as a learning tool?
2. How do podcast media influence the studying habits of tertiary institution students in Lagos state?
3. What is the influence of podcast media on the social behaviour of tertiary institution students in Lagos state?

Conceptual Clarification of Podcast Media

Rime, Pike & Collins (2022) described a podcast as episodic, downloadable or streamable audio material, largely spoken, transmitted over the internet, accessible at any location and time and created by any anyone who desires to do so. Podcasting is a kind of broadcasting that provides the convenience of listening to any program at any time, in contrast to streaming broadcasting. Podcasting consists of a series of digital audio and video recordings disseminated online using Really Simple Syndication (RSS) feeds. Edirisingha *et al* (2007) state that the term "podcasting" comprises two words. The term "iPod" denotes a portable device developed by Apple for the playback of digital music data in the MP3 format. This device allows users to download audio files from their computer or the internet for subsequent listening. The files download automatically upon Internet connection. Podcasts, as a contemporary educational instrument, exhibit unique characteristics that enhance their increasing prevalence in learning contexts.

Basenko & Baskakova (2021) assert that podcasts provide flexibility and mobility in learning, enabling students to access audio resources at any time and from any location, hence improving the accessibility of educational information. They also advocate for autonomous learning, giving students authority over their speed, timing, and location of education. A significant attribute of podcasts is their facilitation of genuine language exposure. They provide learners with authentic linguistic material that facilitates natural learning and enhances listening proficiency (Basenko & Baskakova, 2021). Furthermore, podcasts are shown to enhance learner motivation and engagement owing to their casual style and entertaining format (Basenko & Baskakova, 2021). They emphasise that podcasts augment multimodal learning by engaging both auditory and cognitive processes, hence reinforcing comprehension and retention of knowledge. Moreover, they are cheap and rather simple to produce, making them a compelling resource for both instructors and students (Basenko & Baskakova, 2021).

Literature Review

The perceived use of podcasts by students as a learning tool is crucial to education and may generally impact podcast effectiveness. A number of studies have been done on the use of podcasts, and its relevance on the learning and listening skills. Hassan (2024) conducted a study on the efficacy of podcasting in improving learning outcomes and maintaining student engagement in the Department of Physics at the College of

Education, University of Misan. Findings from the study indicated that the integration of podcasts positively influences academic performance. It concludes by asserting that podcasts assist students in sustaining focus and attention, yet they should not be regarded as a substitute for conventional learning methods. The study advocates for the enhancement of student engagement in podcasting activities outside the conventional classroom environment, promoting discourse and enabling content dissemination. Cao et al. (2024) conducted analogous research on Students' Perceptions of Podcasts as Authentic Materials for Self-Access Listening Practice, by sampling the perceptions of 118 intermediate English linguistics students at International University, Vietnam National University HCMC, concerning the utilisation of podcasts to improve their listening skills outside the classroom. The results indicated favourable perceptions concerning the utility of podcasts for post-classroom listening practice. The participants said that podcasts were beneficial for enhancing their comprehension of spoken language, delivering an interesting and amusing experience and giving flexibility outside conventional classroom environments. The findings of that study demonstrated the efficacy of podcasts as instruments for enhancing English listening abilities, so underscoring the need for educators to contemplate the incorporation of podcasts as a resource for teaching and learning listening skills outside the classroom.

Sengang *et al* (2022) examined students' perceptions regarding the utilisation of podcasts for learning English speaking. The study findings indicated a predominance of favourable replies from questionnaire respondents on students' experiences with podcasts as a learning medium. The study concluded that English podcasts are an effective medium for learning English, particularly for practicing speaking skills. Ifedayo (2023) conducted a study titled "Podcasts Shaping the Educational Landscape: A Comparative Analysis of Nigerian and Foreign Universities," wherein the researchers performed a thematic analysis of tweets pertaining to podcasts and education to investigate the varied and global characteristics of educational discourse on social media platforms. The investigation indicated that educational topics on Twitter highlighted the adaptability of podcasts as a medium for participation. The study's results indicate that podcasts are an effective medium for tackling significant topics, promoting creative practices, and cultivating a worldwide educational community.

Moreover, Ismaila *et al* (2022) conducted a study titled "Impacts and Challenges of Using Podcasting for Teaching and Learning in Higher Educational Institutions in Nigeria." The study emphasised several stages a teacher should adopt when incorporating podcasting into instruction. The researchers highlighted the challenges facing the use of podcasting in Nigeria tertiary institutions, they are: Inadequate access to available resources, inadequate power supply, lack of pedagogical training on how to integrate Podcasting into teaching, inadequate technical support, lack of adequate awareness about educational podcasting, poor implementation of ICT policies by government, insufficient competence in handling ICT resources, high cost of internet service providers, inadequate funding of the university by the government, corruption, Technological obstacles, elevated implementation costs, and substantial expenses associated with e-learning infrastructure. Similarly, David *et al* (2025) examined the influence of online television

streaming platforms on the study habits of private university students in Ogun State. Findings from the study showed that online television streaming platforms even though has become very popular among students, it had no negative influence on the study habits of private university students, except in the area of class attendance. The study by way of recommendations advocated for continuous encouragement and enlightenment on positive use of these streaming platforms by students.

Theoretical Framework

The technology acceptance model formulated by Davis in 1989 is a pivotal framework for comprehending user acceptance of technology. The technology acceptance model posits that two main criteria, perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use influence an individual's desire to adopt a new technology. Perceived usefulness denotes the extent to which an individual believes that utilising a specific system would improve their performance, whereas Perceived Ease of Use signifies the extent to which they believe that employing the system would require minimal effort. Within the realm of podcast media, the technology acceptance model posits that students are more inclined to accept and use podcasts for educational purposes if they believe it enhances their comprehension of academic material (Perceived Usefulness, PU) and if the technology is user-friendly (Perceived Ease of Use, PEOU). The concept asserts that these views affect users' attitudes towards technology; therefore, their desires to utilise it. Research has shown the significance of the technology acceptance model in e-learning contexts. Lee & Lin (2008) discovered that university students' adoption of instructional podcasts was significantly affected by both perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEOU). Likewise, Merhi (2011) demonstrated that intrinsic motivation, when combined with the technology acceptance model, significantly influenced podcast utilisation among students. In Lagos State, where mobile phone usage is high and internet access is improving, technology acceptance model helps explain the varying degrees of podcast adoption among students. If podcasts are perceived as helpful and easy to use, students may be more inclined to integrate them into their study routines. Conversely, if they face challenges such as poor internet connectivity or lack of awareness about educational podcasts, their perceived ease of use and usefulness may be negatively impacted.

Methodology

A quantitative research design by way of survey was adopted for this work. A close-ended questionnaire was employed as a research instrument to gather information from students in (3) selected tertiary institutions which are University of Lagos, Yaba College of Technology and Federal College of Education (Technical), Akoka. These institutions were selected to cut across different spheres of tertiary institutions in Lagos state. As at May 2025, Unilag has a total number of 65,000 students (unilag.edu.ng), YabaTech has a total of 20,000 students as at 2024 (yabatech.edu.ng), while FCE (Technical) has a total number of 2,220 students as of 2024 from the admission officer. Using the Krejcie and Morgan (1970) formula, a sample size of 1129 students was selected for this study. The sampling technique used to establish numbers of the respondents (students) was convenience sampling technique. This technique was selected because of the relatively large number of respondents intended for the study. The researchers positioned

themselves at strategic locations such as the classroom premises, cafeterias, business centers and sport complexes in the selected institutions where the students were easily accessible. Copies of the questionnaire were then distributed evenly across the aforementioned locations. The data were analysed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) where descriptive statistics, frequencies and percentages, were used to present data, and explore the relationships between variables. Therefore, 1129 of the respondents were given a questionnaire, and 1088 copies were properly completed and returned. The selection formula is as follows:

$$n = \frac{n}{1 + (N - 1)e^2}$$

University of Lagos (UNILAG) = 65,000

$$n = \frac{65,000}{1 + (65,000 - 1)0.05^2}$$

$$n = \frac{65,000}{1 + (64,999)0.0025}$$

$$n = \frac{65,000}{1 + 162.4975}$$

$$n = \frac{65,000}{163.4975}$$

$$n = 398$$

Yaba College of Technology (YABATECH) = 20,000

$$n = \frac{20,000}{1 + (20,000 - 1)0.05^2}$$

$$n = \frac{20,000}{1 + (19,999)0.0025}$$

$$n = \frac{20,000}{1 + 49.9975}$$

$$n = \frac{20,000}{50.9975}$$

$$n = 392$$

Federal College of Education (Technical) Akoka (FECA) = 2,220

$$n = \frac{2,220}{1 + (2,220 - 1)0.05^2}$$

$$n = \frac{2,220}{1 + (2,219)0.0025}$$

$$n = \frac{2,220}{1 + 5.5475}$$

$$n = \frac{2,220}{6.5475}$$

$$n = 339$$

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 1: Perception of Tertiary Institution Students in Lagos State on the use of Podcast Media as a Learning Tool

Items	SA Freq. (%)	A Freq. (%)	N Freq. (%)	D Freq. (%)	SD Freq. (%)	\bar{x}	SD
Podcasts are useful for learning.	534 (49.1)	378 (34.7)	104 (9.6)	36 (3.3)	36 (3.3)	1.77	0.98
I have used podcasts for academic purposes.	214 (19.7)	328 (30.1)	270 (24.8)	188 (17.2)	88 (8.1)	2.63	1.20
Podcasts have helped me in my studies.	218 (20)	292 (26.8)	376 (34.6)	132 (12.1)	70 (6.4)	2.58	1.12
Podcasts have benefits as a learning tool.	258 (23.7)	408 (37.5)	302 (27.8)	82 (7.5)	38 (3.5)	2.29	1.02
Podcasts have drawbacks as learning tool.	196 (18.0)	270 (25.0)	442 (40.6)	106 (9.7)	72 (6.6)	2.61	1.09
Average weighted Mean						2.37	1.08

KEY: SA=Strongly Agree, A=Agree, D=Disagree, SD=Strongly Disagree, N=Neutral
 ***Decision Rule if mean is 1 to 1.49 =Neutral; 1.5 to 2.49 = Strongly Disagree; 2.5 to 3.49 = Disagree; 3.5 to 4.49= Agree; 4.5 to 5.00= Strongly Agree

With an average weighted mean of ($\bar{x} = 2.37$) and standard deviation ($SD = 1.08$) as shown in Table 1, it could be inferred from this result that the perception of tertiary institution students in Lagos state concerning the use of the podcast media tilts towards the positive side, perception was measured by sampling the opinion of the students on whether podcasts are useful for learning, how well it has been used by students for academic purposes and helped them in their studies, how it has benefitted them as a learning tool and if it has drawbacks.

Table 2: Influence of the Podcast Media on the Studying Habits of Tertiary Institution Students in Lagos state

Items	SA Freq. (%)	A Freq. (%)	N Freq. (%)	D Freq. (%)	SD Freq. (%)	\bar{x}	SD
Listening to podcasts has changed the way I study and approach learning.	316 (29.0)	292 (26.8)	274 (25.2)	128 (11.8)	78 (7.2)	2.41	1.22
I use podcasts as a supplement for classroom.	154 (14.2)	302 (27.8)	336 (30.9)	204 (18.8)	92 (8.5)	2.79	1.15
I have noticed an improvement in my academic performance since I started listening to podcasts.	186 (17.1)	268 (24.6)	390 (35.8)	154 (14.2)	90 (8.3)	2.71	1.15

Podcasts have helped me stay motivated and engaged in my studies.	230 (21.1)	350 (32.2)	316 (29.0)	112 (10.3)	78 (7.2)	2.50	1.15
I incorporate podcasts into my study routine.	170 (15.6)	254 (23.3)	344 (31.6)	186 (17.1)	132 (12.1)	2.93	2.07
Average Mean						2.66	1.34

Table 2 was used in measuring Influence of the podcast media on the studying habits of tertiary institution students in Lagos state. On the whole, with a mean weighted average of $\bar{x}=2.66$ and standard deviation of 1.34, the participants agree that the podcast media has had a significant influence on the studying habits of tertiary institution students in Lagos state.

Table 3: Influence of the Podcast Media on the Social Behaviour of Tertiary Institution Students in Lagos State

Items	SA Freq. (%)	A Freq. (%)	N Freq. (%)	D Freq. (%)	SD Freq. (%)	\bar{x}	SD
I frequently engage in podcast conversations that spark interesting discussions with others.	386 (35.5)	282 (25.9)	236 (21.7)	108 (9.9)	76 (7.0)	2.27	1.23
I have discovered new interests or hobbies through podcasts.	214 (19.7)	420 (38.6)	250 (23.0)	132 (12.1)	72 (6.6)	2.47	1.13
Podcasts have influenced my social interactions and relationships.	248 (22.8)	366 (33.6)	310 (28.5)	100 (9.2)	64 (5.9)	2.41	1.12
I would not mind starting my own podcast sometime in the future.	278 (25.6)	266 (24.4)	310 (28.5)	150 (13.8)	84 (7.7)	2.53	1.22
Podcasts have broadened my perspectives and understanding of different topics.	286 (26.2)	352 (32.3)	262 (24.0)	100 (9.2)	88 (8.1)	2.40	1.19
Average Mean						2.41	1.17

Table 3 shows the Influence of the podcast media on the social behaviour of tertiary institution students in Lagos state. On the whole, with a mean weighted average of $\bar{x}=2.41$ and standard deviation of 1.17 the participants agree that the podcast media has had a significant and positive influence on the social behaviour of tertiary institution students in Lagos state.

Discussion of Findings

The first objective of the study was to find out the perception of tertiary institution students in Lagos state on the use of podcast media as a learning tool. It could be inferred

from table 1 that the perception of tertiary institution students in Lagos state concerning the use of the podcast media tilts towards the positive side, as students generally hold a positive perception of podcasts as a learning tool, with 83.8% either agreeing or strongly agreeing that podcasts are useful for learning. These findings align with the core assumptions of technology acceptance model which is used to evaluate the perspective of consumer's acceptance of new technology. The podcast media is getting more and more popular especially among young people, as a useful medium of learning, social and interpersonal relationships. Technology acceptance model can be used effectively in predicting perception and use among young people particularly students. The robustness of technology acceptance model has the advantage of wide adaptability and extensibility which are the basis for its effectiveness as a learning tool. Podcasts, by their nature, allow multitasking and repetition, which can enhance information retention. These findings are also in line with the findings of Cao *et al* (2024) who affirmed in his study that there is a positive perception of podcast usefulness in post classroom listening practice. That is students use podcast to facilitate the understanding of a topic outside of classroom activities. In similar research done by Sengang *et al* (2022) which investigated students' perception on the use of podcast to the learning of English speaking. Although the research focused on the learning of English language, but the result showed that students had a positive perception of podcast media for learning. However, both studies confirm that while students perceive podcasts as helpful, they are not fully leveraging them for academic enhancement, possibly due to insufficient guidance from academic stakeholders.

The second objective of this study was to examine the influence of the podcast media on the studying habits of tertiary institution students in Lagos state. Table 2 indicated the participants agree that the podcast media has had a significant influence on the studying habits of tertiary institution students in Lagos state. Findings further showed that podcasts have a moderate but positive influence on the studying habits of students, with an average mean of 2.66. For instance, 55.8% agreed that podcasts have changed the way they study and approach learning. A further 53.3% reported feeling more motivated and engaged in their academic work due to podcasts. Yet, a significant portion of respondents (31.6%) remained neutral on incorporating podcasts into their study routines, suggesting inconsistent integration or unclear benefits. This implies that while students acknowledge the potential of podcasts, they may not have a structured way of using them academically. The table reveals that a total of 38.9% of respondents agreed to incorporating podcast into their study routine while 29.2% strongly disagreed as well as disagree. These findings are reinforced by Hassan (2024), who explored the effectiveness of podcast in enhancing learning outcomes and sustaining students' engagement in the department of physics in the University of Misan. Findings from Hassan's study showed that the incorporation of podcast media had a positive impact on academic achievement.

The third objective of the study was to examine the influence of podcast media on the social behaviour of tertiary institution students in Lagos state. Findings from the study suggest that podcast media is an emerging yet not fully used educational tool among tertiary institution students in Lagos. The technology acceptance model used goes in line

with this as students' attitude to learning has changed since they perceive it to be beneficial to their studies. However, notable limitations remain. The neutral responses across many variables hint at a lack of structured awareness campaigns or institutional support. Moreover, socio-economic barriers such as data affordability and smartphone limitations may continue to restrict consistent podcast use. Despite the high awareness and favorable perceptions, several students reported rarely or never listening to podcasts. This contradiction suggests systemic limitations such as high data costs, low institutional promotion, and lack of academic podcast content aligned with student needs. This is supported by Ismaila & Muhammad (2023), who found that lecturers cited technical, financial, and policy-related challenges as major barriers to integrating podcasts into their teaching. These findings collectively stress the importance of policy-level action to encourage podcast integration, provide staff training, and subsidise tools that allow students to access or create educational podcasts.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concluded that podcasts are emerging as promising educational tools among tertiary students in Lagos State. Awareness of the medium is spreading, but its academic application is still evolving, as entertainment content dominates students' listening habits. Despite this, the potential for podcasts in supporting learning is clear: students find them engaging, easy to access, and well-suited to flexible study routines. The significant relationship between podcast usage and improved studying habits suggests that podcasts can complement traditional learning methods, providing students with supplementary materials they can revisit at their own pace. Similarly, the influence on social behaviour shows that podcasts not only enhance academic engagement but also foster discussions, broaden perspectives, and encourage creativity. However, infrastructural barriers such as internet costs and limited exposure to educational content remain challenges to wider adoption. The study reinforces that podcasting holds substantial potential as a learning tool but remains underutilised due to infrastructural, awareness and curricular integration challenges. Based on the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations are hereby given:

1. Majority of the students perceive podcasts positively and acknowledge their potential for learning, but a significant number do not incorporate them into study routines due to a lack of structure and academic integration. Therefore, tertiary institutions should formally integrate podcasts into the curriculum as supplementary learning materials, particularly for complex or content-heavy courses.
2. Podcasts have a moderate but positive impact on study habits, improving motivation and engagement, but structured adoption remains low. Therefore, academic staff should integrate podcast assignments or reflections into course assessments to encourage active engagement.
3. Institutions can promote blended learning models that include podcast listening as part of pre-class or post-class activities to reinforce learning outside the classroom. This would equally enhance the social and interpersonal skills of students.

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